

Oxy-fuel Combustion of Solid Biomass in Pilot-scale Downdraft Furnace

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Introduction

Solid biomass oxy-fuel combustion with external recirculation was demonstrated in a 100-kW atmospheric down-fired pulverized combustor operated close to stoichiometry. The external recirculation setup comprised a particulate filter, water removal, a fan and mixing with oxygen and helium before the burner inlet. A theoretical description of the recirculation process is given. Two fuels, softwood (SW) and forest residues (FR), with similar residence times, were compared. Major and trace species as well as

gas temperature were quantified in real-time by tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS) at two locations in the reactor core and with Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and mass spectrometry at the exhaust. Gas-phase potassium compounds were measured in the reactor core using photofragmentation TDLAS. Flue gas particles were collected at the exhaust employing a low-pressure impactor and analyzed by X-ray powder diffraction and scanning electron microscopy.

Experimental Setup and Operational Parameters

The one-step chemistry equation describing complete fuel-lean combustion of a fuel containing C, H and O atoms with mole fractions a , b , and c ($a + b + c = 1$), respectively, with an oxidizer containing O_2 and CO_2 can be written as

$$(aC + bH + cO) + dH_2O + \lambda ZO_2 + ACO_2 = (a + A)CO_2 + \left(\frac{b}{2} + d\right)H_2O + \left(\frac{a+b}{4}\right)(\lambda - 1)O_2, \quad (1)$$

where d is the mole fraction of the fuel moisture content, λ is the air-fuel equivalence ratio, $Z = a + b/4 - c/(2\lambda)$, and A is the mole fraction of CO_2 . When the recirculation of dry combustion products is included and assuming that the total mole fraction of O_2 is maintained (fixed overall equivalence ratio), the left part of Eq.(1) can be written as

$$(aC + bH + cO) + dH_2O + \lambda^* Z^* O_2 + Y((a + A)CO_2 + (a+b/4)(\lambda^* - 1)O_2) \quad (2)$$

where λ^* is the air-fuel equivalence ratio calculated neglecting O_2 in recirculated gas, $Z^* = Z(\lambda^*)$, Y is the recirculation coefficient, which characterizes the number of times the dry combustion products are recirculated. The overall oxygen amount in the left parts of Eq.(1) and Eq.(2) is the same, i.e.

$$\lambda Z = \lambda^* Z^* + Y(a + b/4)(\lambda^* - 1). \quad (3)$$

Provided that the overall oxygen concentration in the cold mixture, $[O_2]^c$, is known, Y and λ^* can be evaluated

$$\lambda^* = \frac{\lambda[Z + [O_2]^c(A + a - Z)] - A[O_2]^c}{\lambda Z - [O_2]^c(\lambda Z - a)} \quad (4) \quad Y = \frac{\lambda - \lambda^*}{\lambda^* - 1}. \quad (5)$$

The parameters of the experiments, such as the O_2 and recirculation flows can then be calculated provided the biomass mass flow is known and $[O_2]^c$ is selected prior to the experiment. Table 1 shows the operational parameters: thermal power, global equivalence ratio, input O_2 , CO_2 (fuel line and optical ports flashing), and recirculated flows, O_2 percentage in the cold mixture selected in this work as the set-up values. The reported values correspond to the following pairs of Y and λ^* , for Case 1 0.8 and 1.06 and for Case 2 0.74 and 1.13.

	P	λ	O_2	CO_2	Rec	O_2
	kW		l/m	l/m	l/m	%
Case 1	98	1.11	331	130	357	43
Case 2	98	1.24	353	130	343	48

Table 1. Set up operational values for the reactor, calculated based on SW composition

Figure 1. Schematic of the down-fired pulverized combustor with external recirculation

Results

Figure 2. Real time (a) TDLAS H_2O (Port 1) and FTIR H_2O (b) micro-GC CO_2 , N_2 , O_2 , He (c) FTIR NO and SO_2 measured during oil and FR combustion and combustion of FR with flue gas recirculation.

Figure 3. Average values of SW and FR combustion parameters at Port 1 (open markers) and Port 2 (solid markers) as a function of dry O_2 concentration (Cases 1 and 2) measured by micro-GC at the exhaust. (a, b) TDLAS gas temperature (red markers) and FTIR NO (blue markers), (c, d) H_2O detected by TDLAS and FTIR (blue markers), and CO_2 (red markers) detected by TDLAS and micro-GC, (e, f) CO measured by TDLAS and FTIR (red markers), and soot volume fraction measured by TDLAS (black markers). Data measured for SW oxy-fuel combustion without recirculation, Case OF50 in (Fuel 2025;381:133485), (green markers) are shown for comparison. The error bars indicate the overall measurement uncertainty.

Figure 4. Median concentrations of gaseous atomic potassium (a, b), KOH (c, d), KCl (e, f) and total gaseous K (g, h) measured with PF-TDLAS as a function of dry O_2 concentration at Port 1 (black markers) and Port 2 (orange markers) for SW and FR combustion Cases 1 and 2. Data from SW combustion without recirculation, OF50 in (Fuel 2025;381:133485), (blue markers) are shown for comparison. The TEC predicted K species concentrations are indicated at the top of each panel. The error bars represent the 25th and 75th percentiles of the median values.

Figure 5. (a) Particle size distribution of the fly ash in the flue gas. (b) Morphology of the fumes and the coarse particles in the first fragmentation mode for FR Case 2.

Conclusions

Oxy-fuel combustion of soft wood and forest residues was demonstrated in down-fired pulverized 100 kW reactor using external recirculation of dry flue gases. Stable combustion with recirculation coefficient of about 0.8 was demonstrated for two air equivalence ratios of 1.11 and 1.24. The amount of dry N_2 in flue gases was below 10% for all runs. The TDLAS-measured T and concentrations of CO_2 and H_2O were similar for both fuels indicating complete combustion already inside the reactor. For FR, the exhaust NO concentration was more than four times higher (>1000 ppm) than for SW, correlating with the higher N content of the FR fuel, more than 7 times that of SW. For both fuels, the results indicate the significant CO concentrations. The flue gas from oxy-fuel combustion of FR contained significantly higher amounts of fine and coarse particles than that from SW oxy-fuel combustion. The fine mode particles consisted mainly of

K_2SO_4 and $K_3Na(SO_4)_2$, in excellent quantitative agreement with TECs of gas phase condensation. Apatite was found in the fine mode in the recirculation case. While basically all K present in the fuels was found in the particulate matter, the transformation process is not entirely clear. The measured gaseous K species concentrations were 2-3 times higher for FR than for SW, while the K content in the fuels differed by a factor of 7. In addition, the concentrations of KOH(g) and KCl(g) were significantly lower than the concentrations predicted by TECs, especially for forest residues. These discrepancies could be explained by reaction and uptake of gaseous K by soot, which was present in high amounts, and/or by the relatively high Si and Al content in FR compared to SW, which could limit K vaporization or increase the reaction of gaseous K species with larger flue gas particles.

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